

The Brahmaputra River in India-China Relations: Hydropolitical and Security Dimensions

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Abstract: India-China relations are increasingly shaped by rising freshwater demand, growing competition over transboundary water resources, and the intensifying challenges posed by climate change. Driven by rapid economic growth, populations pressures, and escalating energy requirements, both countries have prioritised hydropower development along the Brahmaputra River (known as the Yarlung Tsangpo in Tibet). China's dam-building and diversion plans have raised significant concerns among riparian states, particularly India, owing to risks such as altered river flows, flash floods, landslides, and broader environmental disruptions. At the same time, India's own efforts to harness the river's hydropower potential further complicate bilateral relations, as competing development strategies contribute to heighten tensions and mutual suspicion. Consequently, the Brahmaputra has emerged as a critical point of contention, reflecting wider hydropolitical and security, and environmental challenges in India-China relations. This paper examines the hydropolitical and security dimensions of the Brahmaputra River dispute, emphasising the need for enhanced transparency, mutual understanding, and cooperative mechanisms to ensure sustainable and equitable transboundary water management.

Keywords: India-China relations, Brahmaputra river, securitisation, water security, hydropolitics, transboundary water management

Introduction

Mansarovar is the highest freshwater lake in the world, fed by the Kailash glaciers near Mount Kailash in the Tibet Autonomous Region (TAR). It is the source of four major rivers in Asia: the Brahmaputra, Ghaghara (a tributary of the Ganges), Sindhu, and Sutlej (a tributary of the Indus) (Baruah, 2018). The Brahmaputra River, stretching approximately 2,880 kilometres, originates in Tibet, where it is known as the Yarlung Tsangpo. It flows eastward through southern Tibet for about 1,625 kilometres before making a dramatic U turn at Shuomatan Point, known as the Great Bend, and entering Arunachal Pradesh, India's easternmost state. In this region, the river is referred to as the Siang. Upon descending into the plains, it is known as the Dihang and, after being joined by its major tributaries, the Dibang and Lohit, it assumes the name Brahmaputra in Assam (Annual Report 2010–11, Government of India).

The Brahmaputra River basin covers an area of approximately 580,000 square kilometres, with 50.5% located in China, 33.6% in India, 8.1% in Bangladesh, and 7.8% in Bhutan (Water Resources Department, Government of Assam; Bossone & Cirasino, 2007). As a major transboundary river shared by China, India, and Bangladesh, the Brahmaputra has long been a source of political and strategic contention. In India, the basin encompasses large parts of Arunachal Pradesh and Assam, as well as areas of Sikkim and West Bengal, complicating efforts to determine equitable water sharing arrangements (Das, 2013).

The Brahmaputra is critically important to North East India, with an average annual runoff from the Tibetan region estimated at approximately 165.4 billion cubic metres (Das, 2013). Any disruption to this flow could have serious consequences for both India and Bangladesh. China's expanding dam building activities on the upper reaches of the river have therefore generated apprehension in India, particularly regarding the risks of flash floods, landslides, and downstream ecological disruption. These concerns were amplified by the catastrophic incident of 9 June 2000, when the collapse of a dam in Tibet triggered sudden flooding in Arunachal Pradesh, resulting in loss of life and extensive damage to infrastructure (Shen, Shi, & Peng, 2020). The absence of timely hydrological data sharing left Indian authorities unprepared for the disaster, reinforcing suspicions and mistrust in bilateral relations. Although subsequent satellite imagery confirmed that the dam failure was accidental, the episode continues to shape India's perceptions of China's upstream activities (Lovelley, 2016).

Rapid economic growth, rising populations, and intensifying competition for energy resources have compelled both China and India to prioritise hydropower development. At the same time, all riparian countries face increasing water stress, exacerbated by climate variability and uneven regional distribution of freshwater resources (Zhang, 2016). Planned hydropower projects and potential water diversion schemes have therefore become significant factors influencing India China relations, heightening concerns over water security and strategic vulnerability (Mahapatra & Ratha, 2016).

Given its role as a lifeline for millions and as a focal point of regional disputes, the Brahmaputra has emerged as a critical factor in India China relations. Much of the existing literature focuses primarily on territorial disputes, often overlooking the river's central role in shaping bilateral tensions as well as opportunities for cooperation. This paper seeks to address this gap by examining the securitisation discourse surrounding the Brahmaputra, the evolution of hydrological diplomacy between India and China, and the geopolitical implications of dam building and water sharing policies.

The completion of the Zangmu Dam, China's first major hydropower project on the Brahmaputra, further intensified these concerns. Announced in 2008 and completed by late 2014, the dam became fully operational by 2015, prompting security analysts to warn of a potential "water conflict" between the two countries. India expressed apprehension over China's initial reluctance to share hydrological data and the perceived lack of transparency surrounding upstream projects. While Chinese authorities have consistently maintained that these dams are run of the river projects intended solely for electricity generation and pose no threat to downstream water flows, India has remained cautious, viewing such developments through the lens of broader strategic rivalry and unresolved border disputes (Lovelley, 2016). By analysing the Brahmaputra through the dual lenses of hydropolitics and security, this study situates the river as both a resource and a strategic instrument in contemporary India–China relations.

Methodology

This paper adopts a qualitative and analytical research methodology to examine the hydropolitical and security dimensions of the Brahmaputra River within the broader framework of India-China relations. The river is treated as a critical transboundary water resource whose

governance is shaped by upstream-downstream power asymmetries, strategic mistrust, and evolving regional security concerns.

The study primarily relies on secondary sources, including government reports, policy documents, academic books, peer-reviewed journals, magazines, newspapers, and credible online resources. The sources are used to analyse scholarly debates on transboundary water governance, hydropolitics, and security, with specific emphasis on water-sharing arrangements, dam-building activities, and data-sharing mechanisms between India and China.

The analysis begins with a review of existing literature to establish a theoretical framework linking hydropolitics with non-traditional security concerns. It then contextualises the historical evolution of the Brahmaputra River in India-China relations, highlighting its geographical and strategic relevance for both countries. Particular attention is given to China's infrastructure development in the upper reaches of the river and India's perceptions of downstream vulnerability, especially in relation to flood risks, ecological impacts, and information asymmetry.

In addition, the study employs selected case studies of past hydrological and dam-related incidents, such as the 2000 dam-related event in Tibet, to illustrate the consequences of inadequate transparency, limited data exchange, and communication gaps between the two Asian giants. These cases help to assess how hydropolitical issues intersect with broader security concerns and bilateral tensions.

The methodology also incorporates an analysis of policy documents, bilateral agreements, confidence-building measures, and institutional mechanisms related to transboundary water management. By synthesising these diverse data sources, the paper identifies gaps in cooperation, evaluates the scope for trust-building, and explores pathways for enhanced institutional dialogue. Ultimately, the study underscores the need for greater transparency, sustained cooperation, and rule-based engagement to manage hydropolitical and security challenges associated with Brahmaputra River in India-China relations.

Securitisation of the Brahmaputra River in India-China Relations

Securitisation refers to the process through which an issue is elevated beyond the realm of conventional political debate and framed as a matter of exceptional importance or as being “above politics” This concept, often described as an “extreme version of politicisation” (Buzan, Wæver & Wilde, 1998), securitisation allows an political actors to portrays an issue as an existential threat, thereby legitimising the suspension of normal political procedures and the adoption of extraordinary measures. According to Copenhagen School, effective securitisation typically involves the identification of an existential threat, the acceptance of emergency responses, and a departure from established norms. However, as Buzan argues, securitisation does not always require the implementation of extreme measures; in many cases, the mere articulation of threat through discourse may be sufficient to securitise an issue.

In the context of the Brahmaputra River, the perception of “existential threats” has significantly shaped India-China relations. The framing of upstream infrastructural projects, particularly dam construction, as security threat has contributed to the emergence of emergency-oriented policy responses. The adoption of a dam-for-dam strategy illustrates how hydrological concerns are increasingly interpreted through a security lens. The construction of large dams as a counter-response

to upstream projects itself represents an extraordinary measure, reflecting the securitised nature of transboundary water governance. Rooted in social constructivism, securitisation theory emphasises that threats are not objective realities but are socially constructed through political discourse. Unlike classical realism, which prioritises power politics, or neorealism, which centres on systematic security imperative (Waltz, 1979; Mearsheimer, 2001), securitisation theory aligns more closely with post-structuralist approaches that highlight actor agency and discursive practices in shaping state behaviour (Vasani, 2023).

The Copenhagen School further conceptualises securitisation as a “speech act” through which an issue is declared an existential threat to a valued referent object. In the case of transboundary rivers, the notion of water wars often emerges from the fear of losing control over freshwater resources and the perceived necessity of ensuring uninterrupted water supplies. Such framing pushes water-related issues beyond the domain of normal politics into the sphere of emergency decision-making (Balzacq, 2005; Schmitt, 1985). India’s discourse on water security frequently draws upon securitisation logic, emphasising existential risks associated with upstream interventions. Ole Wæver captures this sentiment by defining securitisation as the assertion of a “special right to use whatever means are necessary” (Wæver, 1995, p. 55). However, a critical consequence of this security-centric framing is the marginalization of broader socio-environmental concerns and affected stakeholders, resulting in a narrow and state-centric river governance agenda.

As highlighted by Ralf Emmers, securitisation processes are often elite-driven, excluding broader populations and reinforcing top-down decision-making structures (Emmers, 2013, p.134). Similarly, Britt Crow-Miller argues that securitisation functions as a “discourses of deflection,” diverting attention away from essential governance challenges and reframing potentially contentious projects in ways that limit alternative policy options (Crow-Miller, 2015, p.174). In the Brahmaputra basin, this has contributed to the prioritisation of strategic and infrastructural responses over cooperative, ecological, and community-centred approaches to water management.

Securitisation theory also identifies key components within the security framework, including the ‘referent object,’ the securitising actor, and functional actors. The referent object is the entity perceived to face an “existential threat” and deemed worthy of protection (Buzan et al., 1998). In the Brahmaputra River, the referent object extends beyond state sovereignty to include downstream water security, ecological sustainability, and the livelihood of dependent communities. The securitising actors, often state elites, policy-makers, and technocratic institutions or “hydrocrats,” frame Chinese dam construction near the ‘Great Bend,’ as a direct threat to India’s water security and ecological stability. In response, calls for downstream dam construction are frequently justified as necessary countermeasures to regulate water flow and safeguard prior water rights under international norms such as the UN Watercourses Convention.

Functional actors, including non-governmental organisations, advocacy groups, and local communities, have the potential to influence the outcomes of securitisation processes by shaping public discourse and policy debates. However, in region where civil society engagement is limited or where securitised narratives enjoy broad political acceptance, the influence of such actors remains constrained (Vasani, 2023). Consequently, the securitisation of the Brahmaputra River reinforces state-centric and security-driven approaches, often at the expense of inclusive governance and long term hydropolitical cooperation in India-China relations.

Hydropolitics and Security Dimensions of the Brahmaputra River

India and China initiated hydrological cooperation in 1954 through a Memorandum of Understanding aimed at exchanging river related data. This early arrangement was disrupted following the 1962 Sino Indian War, after which cooperation on water issues remained limited for several decades. Tensions resurfaced in 2000 when India accused China of failing to share critical hydrological data concerning the Brahmaputra River. This omission was widely believed to have contributed to severe flooding in Arunachal Pradesh. On 9 June 2000, a catastrophic dam failure in Tibet resulted in a sudden surge of water that inundated the century old town of Pasighat, submerging it under nearly thirty feet of water overnight. This incident was later raised in the Indian Parliament by Member of Parliament Tapir Gao as evidence of the risks posed by inadequate upstream data sharing (Kumar, 2024).

In response to growing concerns, India and China signed another Memorandum of Understanding in 2002 to facilitate the exchange of hydrological information on water levels, discharge, and rainfall from three monitoring stations located at Nugesha, Yangcun, and Nuxia along the Brahmaputra River. Under this arrangement, data are transmitted twice daily via electronic communication from 1 June to 15 October each year (Hodum, 2007). India is required to purchase this data at a mutually agreed price through the India China expert level mechanism on transboundary rivers (Manhas and Yadav, 2022). This cooperation has improved flood forecasting capacity and provided Indian authorities with a clearer understanding of upstream river behaviour. The Memorandum also stipulates that China must notify India of any proposed diversion of the Brahmaputra River (Hodum, 2007).

Despite these institutional mechanisms, India remains apprehensive about China's upstream activities. Central to these concerns are China's proposals to construct a massive hydropower project at the Great Bend of the Yarlung Tsangpo on the Tibetan plateau and to divert water towards its north western provinces. In early 2003, a feasibility study conducted by the China Water Conservancy and Hydropower Planning and Designing Institute estimated that the river segment flowing through Chinese territory possesses a hydropower potential of approximately sixty-eight million kilowatts, accounting for nearly one tenth of China's total capacity. Reports published in People's Daily in 2003 suggested plans for constructing three large dams capable of generating around one hundred thousand megawatts of electricity, second only to the Three Gorges Dam on the Yangtze River. The proposal reportedly included the use of nuclear explosives to construct a fifteen-kilometre tunnel through the Himalayas to redirect the river northwards (People's Daily, 2003).

If implemented, this project could redirect nearly two hundred billion cubic metres of water annually to the Yellow River basin. While such a diversion would significantly benefit China, environmental experts warn that it could reduce the Brahmaputra's downstream flow by up to 60%. Such a decline would have severe consequences for India and Bangladesh, particularly during the dry season, threatening agriculture, hydropower generation in Arunachal Pradesh, and the river-based culture of the lower Brahmaputra basin. These anxieties are intensified by China's broader South North Water Diversion Project, which aims to address water scarcity in northern China.

Additional cooperation mechanisms were established in 2005 and 2006. In April 2005, another Memorandum of Understanding was signed to enable the sharing of water flow data for the Sutlej River during the flood season. In 2006, both countries agreed to establish an expert level mechanism

to facilitate cooperation on hydrological data exchange, emergency preparedness, and flood management. This agreement was finalised during a visit by the Chinese President to India (Roul, 2013). However, in the same year, China denied any intention to divert Brahmaputra waters, leaving Indian concerns largely unresolved.

Chinese officials have consistently denied plans to divert the Brahmaputra. Nevertheless, increasing pressure on China's freshwater resources due to population growth, industrial expansion, and pollution continues to make the river an attractive option for Beijing (Malhotra, 2014). In April 2010, China assured India that dam construction on the Brahmaputra would not affect downstream flows (Prachi, 2011). However, concerns persisted, particularly in Assam, where former Chief Minister Tarun Gogoi urged the central government to closely monitor the downstream impact of hydropower projects on the Yarlung Tsangpo (Talukdar, 2010).

At a conference on water issues in North East India, experts emphasised the need for formal bilateral water agreements between India and China as both states seek to harness the river's resources (Journal of India, 2021). India's own plans for hydropower development on Brahmaputra tributaries have further heightened the sensitivity of the dispute. Transboundary water governance is closely linked with issues of sovereignty, dam safety, and access to drinking water, requiring sustained dialogue and negotiation (Mitra, 2010).

In 2013, another Memorandum of Understanding expanded cooperation on transboundary rivers. Under this agreement, China committed to providing flood season hydrological data for the Brahmaputra River from May to October, extending the previously defined period of June to October (Mahapatra and Ratha, 2016). In 2015, an additional Memorandum of Understanding facilitated data sharing related to the Sutlej River (Manhas and Yadav, 2022). Despite these measures, cooperation remains limited in scope and does not address long term concerns related to infrastructure development and water diversion.

Table 1. Major Transboundary Rivers Between India and China

River	Share by
Indus/ (Shiquan) River	China, India, Pakistan
Brahmaputra/Siang (Yarlung Zangbo) River	China, India, Bangladesh
Sutlej/ (Langqen Zangbo) River	China, India, Pakistan
Kosi/(Arun) River	China, Nepal, India
Ghaghara/ (Kongque/Kongque) River	China, Nepal, India

Source: Xinhuanet and Ministry of Water Resources, Govt. of India.

China occupies the upper riparian position for all the major rivers shared with India. In the cases of the Brahmaputra, Indus, and Sutlej rivers, India functions as a middle riparian state, while it is the lower riparian state for the Kosi and Ghaghara River systems (Zhang, 2016). The Brahmaputra's significance to India is considerable, as it contributes approximately 33% of the country's freshwater resources and 40% of its hydropower potential, underscoring the strategic importance of upstream control (Dhyani, 2022). Tensions along the Brahmaputra are particularly pronounced for three interrelated reasons. First, China controls more than 50% of the Brahmaputra River basin area, enabling it to exert substantial influence over the river's hydrology (Malhotra, 2014). Second, the river is vital to India's agriculture, livelihoods, and energy security, given its substantial contribution

to national freshwater availability. Third, the Brahmaputra's strategic significance is further compounded by unresolved territorial disputes in the Eastern Himalayas.

Water has increasingly become a strategic instrument during periods of political tension. During the Doklam standoff, China withheld hydrological data critical for flood forecasting in India, citing technical issues and station renovations (Palmo, 2017). This explanation was undermined by the continued sharing of similar data with Bangladesh during the same period (Khadka, 2017). Such selective data sharing reinforces perceptions of water being employed as a tool of strategic leverage.

This approach reflects the broader securitisation of water within Chinese foreign policy discourse. Securitisation frames water related challenges as existential threats requiring urgent action (Williams, 2003). In contrast, desecuritisation seeks to return water governance to the realm of normal political negotiation, treating water issues as manageable policy challenges (Waeber, 1993). Chinese commentators have explicitly linked hydrological cooperation to India's respect for Chinese sovereignty, particularly during periods of heightened border tensions (Zhao, 2017).

China's upper riparian position grants it significant leverage over downstream flows. This was evident during the 2020 Galwan Valley incident, when China obstructed the flow of the Galwan River into Indian territory. Although Chinese officials downplay the risks posed by dams on the Brahmaputra, the lack of transparency and selective data sharing continues to fuel mistrust. Unless China adheres consistently to existing Memorandums of Understanding and enhances transparency regarding infrastructure development, hydropolitical tensions along the Brahmaputra are likely to persist, undermining prospects for long term cooperation (Chellaney, 2011).

India's Concern

India's primary concern regarding the Brahmaputra River centres on China's dam construction on the Yarlung Tsangpo and potential diversion plans to meet the water demands of northern and western China, which exceed those of sparsely populated southern Tibet (Limaye, 2015). Debate in India over China's upstream activities intensified in 2005 following the publication of Tibet's Waters Will Save China by Li Ling, an officer in China's Second Artillery Corps. The work proposed strategies for diverting river waters, including 200.6 billion cubic metres from the Brahmaputra, of which 118.8 BCM would affect India's downstream flow (Limaye, 2015). In response, the Indian government convened the Committee of Secretaries (CoS) in 2006 to assess potential impacts, resulting in inter-ministerial studies and monitoring by the National Remote Sensing Agency (NRSA) and the National Technical Research Organisation (NTRO) (Bhaskar, 2015).

China's first major dam on the upper Brahmaputra, the Zangmu Dam, began construction in 2010 and commenced operations in November 2015. The Indian Ministry of External Affairs clarified the government's position in June 2011, noting that the Zangmu project is a run-of-the-river hydroelectric plant that does not store water and is not expected to adversely affect downstream areas (MEA, 2011). Despite this assurance, the adequacy of water flows and the potential downstream impacts have been subjects of debate in India. Estimates suggest that only around 40% of the Brahmaputra's total flow originates from Chinese catchment areas, with Chinese precipitation contributing approximately 7% of the river's volume. Indian policymakers emphasise that rainfall within India and tributaries in Arunachal Pradesh are the primary contributors to the river's flow, which may explain India's measured response to China's upstream activities (Bhaskar, 2014).

Map 1. Zangmu Hydropower Station on Yarlung Zangbo (Siang/Brahmaputra River in India)

Source: *The Indian Express*.

Nevertheless, several experts question these assurances. Brahma Chellaney notes that “China’s dam building is expanding, moving closer to India’s border and providing China with its growing capacity to serve as the upstream controller by re-engineering transboundary flows through dams” (Chellaney, 2015). Former Secretary of Water Resources Ramaswamy Iyer similarly asserts that “for technical hydrological reasons, even China’s run-of-the-river projects are a matter of utmost concern to lower riparian countries” (Ramachandran, 2015). Indian analysts often warn that China’s water ambitions and increasing competition over shared rivers could lead to a future “water conflict,” with political, economic, and security implications.

China’s 14th Five-Year Plan (2021–2025) includes the construction of a new superhydroelectric dam in the lower reaches of the Yarlung Tsangpo, near the Indian border, which is projected to surpass the capacity of China’s Three Gorges Dam with an estimated 60 gigawatts of power generation (Donnellon-May, 2022). In response, India has advanced its own dam projects. The National Hydroelectric Power Corporation (NHPC) submitted a pre-feasibility report for the Upper Siang Multipurpose Storage project in Arunachal Pradesh, anticipated to generate 11 gigawatts and requiring an estimated ₹1.13 trillion investment. NHPC sources note that while hydropower generation is a byproduct, the project primarily aims to counter China’s upstream water diversion plans (Roy, 2023).

China’s dam construction remains a contentious issue in India. While the government maintains a cautious stance, civil society and experts argue that all dams on the Brahmaputra, particularly Chinese projects, present environmental, hydrological, and strategic challenges (Limaye, 2015;

Chellaney, 2009). Indian concerns were heightened in 2017 when the Siang River, a Brahmaputra tributary, turned black, affecting drinking water, agriculture, and ecosystems. Indian authorities attributed the contamination to upstream Chinese activity, while China denied involvement, citing natural causes. The potential for water-related conflict is reinforced by the absence of bilateral or multilateral treaties governing the Brahmaputra (Malhotra, 2014), Chinese assertions over Arunachal Pradesh, and the strategic use of water infrastructure as a political or military tool.

Experts and policymakers continue to raise alarms over China's projects. Dechen Palmo of the Tibet Policy Institute and Tapir Gao, Member of Parliament from Arunachal Pradesh, have described the new superhydropower project as a potential "water bomb." Palmo emphasised that the dam's construction in the seismically active Metok region could have significant environmental and downstream consequences for India and Bangladesh (ANI, 2024). Gao similarly warned that the project could release enormous water volumes unpredictably, posing risks to Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, and Bangladesh, while highlighting India's own dam initiatives to mitigate potential impacts (ANI, 2024). Thus, India's concerns over China's hydropower development on the Brahmaputra are multi-faceted, encompassing environmental, hydrological, strategic, and geopolitical dimensions. With China as the upper riparian power, India remains vigilant over potential reductions in river flow, downstream impacts on agriculture and industry, and the broader implications for regional security and resource competition.

China's Concern

China has expressed its concerns regarding Indian protests against its dam projects on the Brahmaputra River, arguing that India uses these protests to gain sympathy and support from the international community. Beijing maintains that its development projects do not obstruct the river's flow and accuses India of hindering water resource development in Tibet (Zhifei, 2013). China also dismisses India's security concerns as exaggerated propaganda, emphasising its willingness to share water and hydroelectricity with downstream riparian countries. According to Chinese officials, dam construction will benefit not only China but also nations downstream (Zhifei, 2013; Mahapatra & Ratha, 2016).

China further accuses India of constructing reservoirs on the Brahmaputra River to strengthen its control over the disputed region of Arunachal Pradesh (Patranobis, 2013). Beijing perceives India's actions as motivated by self-interest and asserts that the water available from tributary rivers on India's side of the Himalayan frontier should be sufficient for its needs. Moreover, China claims that India deliberately portrays it as a threat to water security, despite India's substantial consumption of water resources (Rosenfield, 2010).

Hydropower is a critical resource for China to address energy shortages and promote economic growth. The country faces significant regional water disparities: northern China, with approximately 500 million people, has access to only a fifth of the nation's freshwater, while the southern region, home to 700 million people, receives four-fifths of available water. To mitigate this imbalance, China is pursuing projects to redirect water from various sources to northern regions (Mishra, 2010).

Additionally, China assures India that it will responsibly utilise and protect water resources in the Trans-Himalayan rivers that flow from Chinese territory into India. These rivers, located at an average altitude of 4,000 metres, serve multiple purposes, including electricity generation and flood

control. China characterises its dam projects as run-of-river schemes that focus on power generation without storing water, thereby minimising ecological and environmental impacts on downstream countries. The Chinese government stresses principles of fairness, rationality, and the protection of the interests of developing regions in the planning and execution of these projects (Mahapatra & Ratha, 2016).

Downstream Vulnerabilities: Implications for Bangladesh

The most significant impact of any upstream diversion of the Brahmaputra River by China is likely to be felt in Bangladesh, the most underdeveloped and densely populated country within the river basin. The Brahmaputra-Padma River is of critical importance to Bangladesh, and any diversion by China would result in environmental degradation across large parts of the country. Bangladesh is heavily dependent on transboundary water flows, with approximately 91% of its water supply originating outside its borders, amounting to nearly 1,105.6 cubic kilometres (km³) of river water annually (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations, 2010). If China's mega projects were to reduce the flow of the Brahmaputra River into India and Bangladesh, downstream regions would suffer the most severe consequences, affecting multiple sectors ranging from agriculture to livelihoods and human security.

Conclusion

The discussion highlights the complex and often contentious dynamics between India and China in the management of transboundary water resources, particularly the Brahmaputra River. China's expanding dam-building activities and the possibility of large-scale water diversion have generated significant apprehension in India, especially regarding their implications for river flow, agricultural productivity, and downstream communities. While China maintains that its projects are primarily intended for hydropower generation and pose no threat to downstream water availability, India continues to perceive these initiatives as potential strategic risks. These concerns are further intensified by limited transparency and inconsistent communication, which contribute to mistrust and heightened tensions in bilateral relations.

Addressing these challenges requires sustained dialogue and the strengthening of institutional mechanisms for transboundary water governance. The establishment of a joint or multilateral framework for data sharing, information exchange, and coordinated river management could help reduce uncertainty and foster greater predictability in India–China relations. Past experiences of restricted hydrological data sharing underscore the importance of institutionalised cooperation in building confidence between the two countries.

As regional security analysts caution against the escalation of water-related disputes into broader strategic confrontations, the need for cooperative solutions becomes increasingly evident. Effective and inclusive management of the Brahmaputra River has the potential not only to ease bilateral frictions but also to promote long-term trust, regional stability, and sustainable development. By viewing the Brahmaputra as a shared resource rather than a source of rivalry, India and China can transform hydropolitical challenges into opportunities for constructive engagement.

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